

Friedel-Crafts Reaction with Arylcarbinols : One-Pot Synthesis of 10-Methylbenzo[*a*]fluoranthene[†]

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Friedel-Crafts reaction with some monoaryl and diaryl carbinols have been studied. The products suggest a rational mode of formation of trityl alcohol and anthracene derivatives modifying the earlier reported conjecture of their formation from carbon monoxide, generated from benzhydrol and solvent benzene. It now appears that during Friedel-Crafts reaction the benzyl carbocation generated from benzhydrol may be arylated to triphenylmethane derivative. The latter under the experimental condition forms trityl cation which abstracts the hydroxyl group from the benzhydrol to form benzyl carbocation and trityl alcohol. Benzyl carbocations act both as a nucleophile and an electrophile and dimerize to form anthracene derivatives. Incidentally, a one-pot synthesis of 10-methylbenzo[*a*]fluoranthene (26), characterized by NOE, decoupling and mass spectral studies, has been achieved in good yield by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of 9-fluorenenol, thus providing a simple method of its synthesis.

Several fluorenones¹⁻⁴, viz. dengibsin (1), dengibsinin (2), dendroflorin (3), dendrochrystin (4) and dendrochrystinin (5) were isolated in this laboratory from some Orchidaceae plants and we became interested in their synthesis. It is known⁵ that benzoic acid (6) undergoes anhydrous AlCl₃ induced cyclization to form fluorene-9-carboxylic acid (7). We, therefore, planned to prepare the intermediate substrates required for the synthesis of the above fluorenones through such cyclization of suitably substituted benzhydrol derivatives.

With a view to synthesizing 1,4-dimethoxyfluorene (8) as the model compound, 2,5-dimethoxybenzhydrol (9) was prepared by Friedel-Crafts reaction of 1,4-dimethoxybenzene with benzoyl chloride, followed by sodium borohydride reduction of the resulting benzophenone derivative. Compound 9 when subjected to Friedel-Crafts reaction in benzene gave 2,5-dimethoxydiphenylmethane (10)⁶ as the major product instead of 8 along with 1,4-bis(diphenylmethyl)-2,5-dimethoxybenzene (11)⁷, trityl alcohol (12) and a trace amount of diphenylmethane (13).

It has been reported⁸ that benzhydrol (14) when heated with anhydrous AlCl₃ in benzene at 60° for 3 h yielded 12 and anthracene (15) and these products have been suggested to originate from carbon monoxide generated from benzhydrol under experimental condition and the solvent benzene. However, the fortuitous formation of 10 and 11 in our case sheds light on the possible mode of formation of 12 and 15. The formation of trityl alcohol (12) can be explained as shown in Scheme 1. The phenylation of benzyl carbocation formed from 9 as well as 14 leads to the formation of the corresponding triphenylmethane derivative. Fur-

- 1 : R = OH, R¹ = R² = R⁴ = H, R³ = R⁵ = OMe
2 : R = R⁴ = OH, R¹ = R² = H, R³ = R⁵ = OMe
3 : R = R¹ = R⁵ = OH, R² = R⁴ = H, R³ = OMe
4 : R = R² = R⁵ = OH, R¹ = R⁴ = H, R³ = OMe
5 : R = R² = R⁴ = OH, R¹ = H, R³ = R⁵ = OMe

ther truncation of the triphenylmethane derivative formed from 9 gives rise to simple biphenylmethine carbocation (19), the latter on one more phenylation yields triphenyl-

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev with profound regards on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

methane (20) as in case of 14. From triphenylmethane, hydride is abstracted under Friedel-Crafts condition to form trityl cation (16). The latter can remove the hydroxyl group from the benzhydrol and substituted benzhydrol to form trityl alcohol (12)⁹.

The above scheme has an analogy. Newman¹⁰ suggested that trityl cation (16) attacked the methoxy group of the *ortho*-ester (17) to give trityl methyl ether and the ambient cation (18) (Scheme 2).

To substantiate our conjecture we analysed the product profile of benzhydrol and some substituted benzhydrols as well as benzyl alcohols under similar experimental conditions. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Compound 11 is likely to be formed from two molecules of 10. One molecule of 10 is truncated by benzylic cleavage to generate biphenylmethine carbocation (19). The latter serves as the alkylating agent and can alkylate 10 to form 11. The carbocation 19 can also alkylate benzene to form triphenylmethane 20. Compound 20 is not reported to be formed from benzhydrol with excess of AlCl_3 (3 mol) at 60°, while at 0° with 1 mole AlCl_3 , 20 is the sole product. Perhaps 20 is formed initially, but at higher temperature with excess of AlCl_3 , it formed 16 which attacks hydroxyl group of benzhydrol generating a diphenylmethine carbocation. The latter can be arylated by benzene to generate 20. Triptyl alcohol being less soluble, the equilibrium will be shifted in favour of it. In case of 9-fluorene (21), biphenyl is obtained as the major product, while the other product has been identified as 9-phenylfluorene (22)^{11,12}. Biphenyl is obtained in all the cases and is supposed to be formed from the solvent¹². However, the greater yield of biphenyl in case of 9-fluorene may be due to the presence of biphenyl system in the molecule of 9-fluorene. Fragmentation products are known to be formed during Friedel-

TABLE 1—FRIEDEL-CRAFTS REACTION PRODUCTS OF BENZHYDROLS

Substrate/(solvent, 80°)	Products, (m.p. °C, yield%)
Benzhydrol (14) (PhH)	Anthracene (15, 211°, 1.5), trityl alcohol (12 ^a , 156°, 48), biphenylmethane (trace), biphenyl (trace)
2,5-Dimethoxybenzhydrol (9) (PhH)	2,5-Dimethoxydiphenylmethane (10, 102°, 19), 1,4-bis(diphenylmethyl)-2,5-dimethoxybenzene (11, 202°, 0.7), trityl alcohol (12, 156°, 26), biphenylmethane (13, trace), biphenyl (21, 71°, trace)
1-Phenylethanol (24) (PhH)	9,10-Dimethylantracene (23, 179°, 24), diphenylmethane (trace), liquid (unidentified)
9-Fluorene (21) (PhH)	9-Phenylfluorene (22 ^b , 143–44°, 20), biphenyl (35)
9-Fluorene (21) (PhMe)	10-Methylbenzo[<i>a</i>]fluoranthene (26, 128°, 55.5), fluorene (24, 115°, 1.1), biphenyl (21, 71°, 27)
Benzyl alcohol (PhH)	Anthracene (15, 36), diphenylmethane (trace)
Benzyl alcohol (PhMe)	2,6-Dimethylantracene (25), 2,7-dimethylantracene (25')

^aRef. 12. ^bRef. 13.

Crafts reaction initiated by fragmentation of diphenylalkane, and triphenylalkane leading to carbocations followed by intermolecular alkylation, arylation and hydrogen transfer—a quite common feature of side-reactions in Friedel-Crafts reactions. Thus benzylic cleavage of 9-phenylfluorene (22) must have yielded biphenyl in the above fashion. Had anthracene and trityl alcohol been formed from carbon monoxide generated from benzhydrols and solvent benzene, these two products would have been obtained in these cases, which is not the observation (Table 1). 9-Fluorene on treatment with AlCl_3 in toluene in an analogous fashion gives 10-

Scheme 3 : Probable mechanism of the formation of anthracene (15). Reagents and condition: (i) AlCl_3 , PhH, 80°, 3 h. (ii) aerial [O].

Scheme 4. Probable mechanism of the formation of 9,10-dimethylanthracene (23). Reagents and condition: (i) AlCl_3 , PhH, 80° , 3 h, (ii) aerial [O].

methylbenzo[*a*]fluoranthene (26) in 55.5% yield along with biphenyl and fluorene. However, the formation of biphenyl in absence of benzene in this case conclusively suggests its origin from fluorenoyl. Surprisingly no 9-tolylfluorene could be obtained.

The formation of anthracene (15) and 9,10-dimethylanthracene (23) from benzhydrol and 1-phenylethanol (24) respectively may well be explained in terms of benzylic carbocation intermediate which can act both as an electrophile and a nucleophile in two steps leading to dimerization followed by aromatization to yield anthracene and 23 (Schemes 3 and 4). The formation of 2,6-dimethylanthracene (25) and 2,7-dimethylanthracene (25') from benzyl alcohol and toluene may also be explained in terms of benzylic carbocation intermediate (Scheme 5). The formation

of 26 has been rationalized (Scheme 6). The structure of 10-methylbenzo[*a*]fluoranthene has been elaborated from a careful analysis of its spectral data. The ir spectrum showed strong absorption for the aromatic system. The assignments of all the protons appearing in its ^1H nmr spectrum were

Scheme 5. Probable mechanism of the formation of 2,6-dimethylanthracene (25) and 2,7-dimethylanthracene (25'). Reagents and condition: (i) AlCl_3 , PhH, 80° , 3 h, (ii) aerial [O].

TABLE 2—DECOUPLING EXPERIMENTS OF 10-METHYLBENZO[*a*]FLUORANTHENE (2)

Signal irradiated		Signals affected				
δ -value	Assignment	δ -value	Assignment	Original multiplicity	Multiplicity after irradiation	Relation disposition of the concerned protons
7.40	H-5	7.48	H-6	dd (6.8, 1.4)	d (7.4)	<i>ortho</i>
		8.04	H-4		bs ($W_{1/2}$ 1)	
7.48	H-6	7.40	H-5	dt (7.4, 7.4 and 1.2) bd (10, $W_{1/2}$ of each signals at 2Hz)	dd (7.4, 1.2)	<i>ortho</i>
		8.38	H-7		s	
7.65	H-2	7.99	H-1	d (8.4) d (6.7)	s	<i>ortho</i>
		8.00	H-3		s	
7.90	H-11	7.51	H-9	dd (7.4, 1.3)	d (7.5)	<i>meta</i>
8.00	H-3	7.65	H-2	dd (8.4 and 6.5)	d (6.2)	<i>ortho</i>
8.04	H-4	7.40	H-5	dt (7.4, 7.4, 1.2) dt (7.5, 7.5, 1.4)	dd (7.5, 1.5)	<i>ortho</i>
		7.48	H-6		t (7.5, 7.5)	
8.37	H-7	7.40	H-5	dt (7.4, 7.4, 1.2)	t (7.4, 7.4)	<i>meta</i>
8.38	H-12	7.48	H-6	dt (7.5, 7.5, 1.4)	dd (7.4, 1.4)	<i>ortho</i>
8.67	H-8	7.51	H-9	dd (7.4, 1.3)	d (1.3)	<i>ortho</i>

Scheme 6. Probable mechanism of the formation of 26. Reagents and condition : (i) AlCl_3 , 80° , (ii) AlCl_3 , toluene, 80° , 3 h, (iii) aerial [O].

made from extensive decoupling experiments and some NOE studies. The results are displayed in Table 2 and its ^{13}C nmr spectral data are given in Table 3.

When the signals at δ 7.40 (H-5) was irradiated, the multiplet at δ 7.48 (H-6) collapsed from a dt (J 7.4, 7.4, 1.4 Hz) to a bd (J 7.4) and that at δ 8.04 (H-4) collapsed from a dd (J 6.8, 1.4) to a bs ($W_{1/2}$ 1) thus evincing the *ortho* orientation of each of the affected protons with respect to the proton irradiated. When the signals at δ 7.48 (H-6) was saturated, the multiplicity of the signals at δ 7.40 (H-5) collapsed from the original dt (J 7.4, 7.4, 1.2) to a dd (J 7.4, 1.2) and that at δ 8.38 (H-7) collapsed from the original d (J 4) to an s, confirming the *ortho* disposition of both protons affected with respect to the proton signals irradiated. Irradiation of δ 7.65 signals (H-2) caused the collapse of each of the doublet signals at δ 7.99 (H-1, J 8.4) and 8.00 (H-3, J 6.7) to a singlet, again confirming the *ortho* disposition of the protons whose signals are affected with respect to the proton being irradiated. The irradiation of H-11 signal at δ 7.90 caused the collapse of the δ 7.51 signal due to

TABLE 3— ^{13}C NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF 10-METHYLBENZO[*a*]FLUORANTHENE

Chemical shift (δ)	Plausible assignment	Chemical shift (δ)	Plausible assignment
140.30	C-3b	127.37	C-6
138.90	C-12b	126.91	C-1
136.67	C-7a	126.20	C-12
134.67	C-3a	126.14	C-9
134.03	C-10, C-12a	123.74	C-8
130.00	C-7b	123.47	C-4
129.91	C-2	21.68	CH_3
128.64	C-11	—	—
127.58	C-11a	121.41	C-3
127.37	C-7c	119.57	C-7

H-9 from a dd (J 7.4, 1.3) to a d (J 7.5) thus confirming the *meta* disposition of the irradiated and affected protons. The irradiation of the δ 8.04 signal (H-4) resulted in the collapse of the multiplicity of the signals at δ 7.48 (H-6) from a dt (J 7.5, 7.5, 1.4) to a t (J 7.5, 7.5) and that at δ 7.40 (H-5) from a dt (7.4, 7.4, 1.2) to a dd (7.5, 1.4), confirming the *ortho* disposition of each of affected protons. This irradiation caused the saturation of the very close by signal at δ 8.00 (H-3) effecting the collapse of the dd signals (J 8.4, 6.5) at δ 7.65 (H-2) to a d (6.2 Hz), again confirming the *ortho* disposition of the responsible protons. Again when the signals at δ 8.38 (H-7) was irradiated, the multiplet at δ 7.40 (H-5) collapsed from dt (J 7.4, 7.4, 1.2) in the original spectrum to t (J 7.4, 7.4) confirming the assignment of the multiplets to the specified *meta* protons; at the same time the multiplet at δ 7.8 (H-6) collapsed from a dt (J 7.5, 7.5, 1.4) to a d (J 7.4) confirming the *ortho* disposition of the concerned protons. The signals at δ 8.65 (H-8) upon irradiation caused the collapse of the dd at δ 7.51 (J 7.4 and 1.3, H-9) to a doublet (J 1.3), confirming the *ortho* orientation of the protons responsible for these signals. When the signals at δ 7.90 (H-11) was irradiated the same signals at δ 7.51 collapsed from a dd as stated before to a d (J 1.3 Hz), confirming the *ortho* assignments of the concerned protons.

The structure 14 was finally confirmed by NOE experiments. The proton at δ 8.38 (H-7) showed NOE by 6.2% when the proton at δ 8.65 (H-8) was irradiated. When the CH_3 group was irradiated, the protons at δ 7.9 and 7.55 (H-11 and H-9) showed NOE by 6.5 and 4.92% respectively. The proton at δ 8.37 (H-12) showed NOE by 4.03% when the proton at δ 7.90 (H-11) was irradiated.

The ^{13}C nmr spectrum was taken in CDCl_3 at 75 MHz. The chemical shift values with their probable assignments are delineated in Table 3.

Experimental

M.ps. measured in open capillary tubes are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were measured on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. ^1H nmr (at 300 MHz) and ^{13}C nmr spectra (at 75.5 MHz) were recorded in CDCl_3 on a Bruker-300A spectrophotometer; the peak for TMS or solvent (CHCl_3 : δ 7.26 or CDCl_3 : δ 77.0) was used as internal standard; J values are expressed in Hz. Light petrol used had b.p. 60–80°. Silica gel (60–120 mesh, Qualigen) was used for column chromatography and silica gel G for the monitoring.

Reaction of 2,5-dimethoxybenzhydrol (9) with AlCl_3 : Isolation of 2,5'-dimethoxyphenyldiphenylmethane (10), 1,4-bis(diphenylmethyl)-2,5-dimethoxybenzene (11), trityl alcohol (12) and diphenylmethane (13) : To dry benzene (80 ml), 2,5-dimethoxybenzhydrol (4.2 g, 0.17 mol) was added dropwise while stirring. It was then cooled in an ice-bath till a crystalline mass was obtained. AlCl_3 (7 g, 0.052 mol) was then added in one lot. The reaction mixture turned deep green after some time. It was heated on an oil-bath (80°) for 3 h, then cooled and decomposed with crushed ice (5 g), water (35 ml) and concentrated HCl (17.5 ml). It was then extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water (4×25 ml), saturated NaHCO_3 solution (3×25 ml) and finally with water (3×25 ml) till it was neutral to pH paper, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated to give a brown residue. The residue was chromatographed over silica gel (60–120 mesh). The light petrol (b.p. 40–60°) eluates afforded trace amount of diphenylmethane (13).

The light petrol (b.p. 60–80°) eluates afforded 1,4-bis(diphenylmethyl)-2,5-dimethoxybenzene (11) crystallizing from chloroform-methanol in needles (50 mg, 0.7%), m.p. 205° (lit.⁷ 207°); ν_{max} 1595, 1580, 1490, 1468, 1445, 1390, 1330, 1250, 1208, 1175, 1150, 1072, 1042, 1030, 927, 875, 855, 820, 760, 740, 720, 695, 650, 630, 610 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 7.8–7.28 (20H, m, C_6H_5), 6.44 (2H, s, H-3 and H-6), 5.88 (2H, s, H-1 and H-1'), 3.4 (6H, s, OCH_3 at C-2 and C-5); ^{13}C nmr δ 151.16 (C-2), 143.96 (C-1'), 131.5 (C-1), 129.41 (C-2'), 128.10 (C-3'), 126.04 (C-4'), 114.21 (C-6), 56.32 (OCH_3), 48.21 (methine carbon).

The later light petrol eluates afforded 2,5-dimethoxyphenyldiphenylmethane (10) crystallizing from chloroform-methanol in white needles (0.926 g, 18.59%), m.p. 102° (lit. 104°); ν_{max} 1600, 1495, 1460, 1445, 1430, 1410, 1320, 1300, 1290, 1240, 1215, 1170, 1150, 1095, 1075, 1040, 1020, 950, 855, 825, 810, 800, 750, 740, 700, 630, 620, 600 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 7.27–7.08 (10H, m, C_6H_5), 6.81 (1H, d, J 8, H-3), 6.7 (1H, dd, J 8.3, H-4), 6.46 (1H, d, J 3, H-6), 5.89 (1H, s, H-1), 3.66 and 3.65 (3H, s, OCH_3 at C-2 and C-5); ^{13}C nmr δ 151.52 (C-2), 153.24 (C-5), 143.47 (C-1'), 133.83 (C-1), 129.19 (C-2'), 127.92 (C-3'), 125.87

(C-4'), 117.19 (C-6), 110.89 (C-4), 111.57 (C-3), 55.91 (OCH_3), 55.14 (OCH_3), 49.63 (methine carbon).

The light petrol-ethyl acetate (97:3) eluates afforded trityl alcohol, crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol in needles, (1.06 g, 26.10%), m.p. 162° (lit.⁹ 164°); ν_{max} 3400, 1600, 1485, 1440, 1325, 1165, 1030, 1010, 930, 910, 885, 765, 695, 635 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 7.34–7.24 (15H, m, C_6H_5), 2.83 (1H, s, exchangeable with D_2O , OH at C-1); ^{13}C nmr δ 146.77 (C-1), 127.76 (C-2, C-3, C-5 and C-6), 127.09 (C-4), 81.90 (carbinol carbon).

Reaction of benzhydrol (14) with AlCl_3 : Isolation of trityl alcohol (12), diphenylmethane (13) and anthracene (15) : Benzhydrol (2 g, 0.01 mol) in dry benzene (80 ml) was stirred on an ice-bath till a crystalline mass was obtained. AlCl_3 (5 g, 0.03 mol) was then added to it in one lot. The solution turned deep green after sometime. The reaction mixture was then heated on an oil-bath at 80° for 3 h, then cooled, decomposed with crushed ice (5 g), water (35 ml) and concentrated HCl (17.5 ml) and extracted with ether (4×20 ml). The ethereal layer was separated, washed with water (4×25 ml), saturated NaHCO_3 (3×20 ml) and finally with water (4×20 ml), dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated to give a brown residue. Chromatography of the residue over silica gel afforded trace amount of diphenylmethane (13), m.p. 26° from the light petrol (b.p. 40–60°) eluates.

The light petrol (b.p. 60–80°) eluates yielded anthracene, crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol in white flakes (0.050 g, 1.37%), m.p. 210°; ν_{max} 1612, 1525, 1440, 1310, 1262, 1160, 1140, 990, 950, 900, 875, 720, 590 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 8.38 (2H, s, H-9 and H-10), 8.03–7.99 (4H, m, H-1, H-4, H-5 and H-8), 7.50–7.46 (4H, m, H-2, H-3, H-6 and H-7).

The light petrol-ethyl acetate (97 : 3) eluates afforded trityl alcohol (12) crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol in needles (1.35 g, 47.8%), m.p. 162°.

Reaction of benzyl alcohol with AlCl_3 : Isolation of diphenylmethane (13) and anthracene (15) with benzene as solvent and a mixture of 2,7-dimethylantracene (25') and 2,6-dimethylantracene (25) with toluene as solvent : To dry benzene (80 ml), benzyl alcohol (4 g, 0.04 mol) was added dropwise while stirring. The solution was cooled on an ice-bath till a crystalline mass was obtained. AlCl_3 (14.85 g, 0.11 mol) was then added in one lot. The reaction mixture was heated on an oil-bath at 80° for 3 h. Then it was cooled, decomposed with crushed ice (5 g), water (35 ml) and concentrated HCl (17.5 ml) and extracted with ether (5×30 ml). The organic layer was separated, washed with water (4×25 ml), saturated NaHCO_3 solution (3×20 ml) and water (4×25 ml) and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 .

Removal of ether gave a brown residue which was purified by chromatography over silica gel. The light petrol (b.p. 40–60°) eluates afforded trace amount of diphenylmethane (13).

The light petrol (b.p. 60–80°) eluates afforded anthracene (15) crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol in flakes (2.325 g, 36%), m.p. 211°.

The reaction was repeated taking dry toluene (80 ml) as the solvent instead of dry benzene. Usual workup followed by chromatography of the residue over silica gel (100–200 mesh) afforded a chromatographically inseparable mixture of 2,6-dimethylantracene **25** and 2,7-dimethylantracene **25'** from the light petrol (b.p. 60–80°) eluates. The following spectral data were taken to identify the components of the mixture: ν_{\max} 1520, 1450, 1370, 1300, 1265, 1030, 960, 920, 895, 890, 860, 785 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 8.30 (1H, s, H-10 of 2,7-dimethylantracene), 8.24 (2H, s, H-9 and H-10 of 2,6-dimethylantracene), 8.18 (1H, s, H-9 of 2,7-dimethylantracene), 7.86 (2H, d, *J* 8, H-4 and H-5 of 2,7-dimethylantracene and H-4 and H-8 of 2,6-dimethylantracene), 7.70 (2H, s, H-1 and H-8 of 2,7-dimethylantracene and H-1 and H-5 of 2,6-dimethylantracene), 7.26 (2H, d, *J* 8, H-3 and H-6 of 2,7-dimethylantracene and H-3 and H-7 of 2,6-dimethylantracene), 3.60 (6H, s, CH_3); ^{13}C nmr δ 132.12 (C-2 and C-6), 130.46 (C-12 and C-14), 128.19 (C-1 and C-5), 126.24 (C-4 and C-8), 125.13 (C-3 and C-7), 123.82 (C-9 and C-10), 21.06 (CH_3).

Reaction of 1-phenylethanol with AlCl_3 : Isolation of 9,10-dimethylantracene (23) : To dry benzene (80 ml), 1-phenylethanol (2 g, 0.01 mol) was added dropwise while stirring. The solution was cooled on an ice-bath till a crystalline mass was obtained. AlCl_3 (6.6 g, 0.04 mol) was then added at once. The reaction mixture was then heated on an oil-bath at 80° for 3 h. Then it was cooled, decomposed with crushed ice (5 g), water (35 ml) and concentrated HCl (17.5 ml) and extracted with ether (4×25 ml). The organic layer was separated, washed with water (4×20 ml), saturated NaHCO_3 (5×20 ml), water (4×20 ml) and dried over Na_2SO_4 . Removal of the ether followed by column chromatography of the residue over silica gel afforded a bluish green semisolid from the light petrol (b.p. 60–80°) eluates. This on repeated chromatography over silica gel (100–200 mesh) afforded 9,10-dimethylantracene (**23**) crystallising from chloroform-light petrol in bluish green flakes (0.686 g, 23.3%), m.p. 179°; ν_{\max} 1610, 1520, 1440, 1380, 1370, 1360, 1180, 1160, 1020, 940, 840, 810, 750, 740, 600 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 8.32–8.26 (4H, m, H-1, H-4, H-5 and H-8), 7.51–7.46 (4H, m, H-2, H-3, H-6 and H-7), 3.06 (6H, s, CH_3 at C-9 and CH_3 at C-10); ^{13}C nmr δ 129.79 (C-11, C-12, C-13 and C-14), 128.19 (C-9 and C-10), 125.18 (C-

1, C-4, C-5 and C-8), 124.56 (C-2, C-3, C-6 and C-7), 29.59 (CH_3).

*Reaction of 9-fluoreneol with AlCl_3 : Isolation of 9-phenylfluorene (22), biphenyl (21) with benzene as solvent and isolation of biphenyl (21), fluorene (24) and 10-methylbenzo[*a*]fluoranthene (26) with toluene as solvent* : A solution of 9-fluoreneol (2 g, 0.016 mol) in benzene (30 ml) was stirred on an ice-bath till a crystalline mass was obtained. AlCl_3 (5 g, 0.037 mol) was then added to it in one lot. The reaction mixture was heated on an oil-bath at 80° for 3 h. It was then cooled and decomposed with crushed ice (5 g), water (35 ml) and concentrated HCl (17.5 ml). Stirring was discontinued and the residue was extracted with ether (4×25 ml). Removal of ether followed by repeated column chromatography of the residue over silica gel (100–200 mesh) afforded 9-phenylfluorene (**22**) from the light petrol (b.p. 60–80°) eluates. The compound was crystallized from chloroform-light petrol in white needles (0.515 g, 19.4%), m.p. 143–144° (lit.¹³ 148°); ν_{\max} 1600, 1490, 1450, 1445, 1290, 1150, 1090, 1070, 1030, 1000, 945, 940, 910, 880, 870, 840, 780, 750, 740, 720, 695, 620, 610, 600 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 7.77 (2H, d, *J* 7, H-4 and H-5), 7.37–7.16 (9H, m, H-2, H-3, H-6, H-7, C_6H_5), 7.06–7.04 (2H, m, H-1, H-8), 5.02 (1H, s, H-9); ^{13}C nmr δ 147.78 (C-4), 141.18 (C-12), 140.39 (C-14), 128.54 (C-3 and C-6), 128.20 (C-2 and C-7), 127.16 (C-2', C-3', C-5' and C-6'), 126.68 (C-1 and C-8), 125.19 (C-4'), 119.72 (C-4 and C-5), 54.34 (C-9).

The light petrol (b.p. 40–60°) eluates afforded a low melting semisolid which on repeated chromatography yielded biphenyl (**21**), crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol in colourless needles (0.45 g, 26.6%), m.p. 71°; ν_{\max} 1600, 1575, 1485, 1450, 1435, 1400, 1350, 1270, 1050, 1010, 960, 910, 735, 705, 615 cm^{-1} .

The reaction was repeated using dry toluene (80 ml) instead of dry benzene. Usual work-up followed by column chromatography over silica gel afforded fluorene (**24**) from the light petrol (b.p. 40–60°), crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol in white needles (0.02 g, 1.09%), m.p. 110° (lit.¹⁹ 116°). The light petrol (b.p. 60–80°) eluates afforded biphenyl (**21**), crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol in colourless needles (0.450 g, 26.62%), m.p. 71.

The residue obtained from the ethyl acetate-light petrol (1 : 99) eluates on repeated chromatography over silica gel (100–200 mesh) afforded 10-methylbenzo[*a*]fluoranthene (**26**) crystallizing from chloroform-light petrol in needles (0.81 g, 55.5%), m.p. 128°; ν_{\max} 1570, 1520, 1470, 1440, 1400, 1380, 1180, 880, 860, 850, 815, 790, 785, 750, 730, 610 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ 8.67 (1H, d, *J* 9.1, H-8), 8.38 (1H, bd, *J* 10, $W_{1/2}$ of each signal 2 Hz, H-7), 8.37 (1H, s, H-12),

8.04 (1H, dd J_o 6.8, J_m 1.4, H-4), 8.00 (1H, d, J 6.7, H-3), 7.99 (1H, d, J 8.4, H-1), 7.90 (1H, bs, $W_{1/2}$ 5, H-11), 7.65 (1H, dd, J_o 8.4 and 6.5, H-2), 7.51 (1H, dd, J_o 7.4, J_m 1.3, H-9), 7.48 (1H, dt, $J_o=J_o$ 7.5, J_m 1.4, H-6), 7.40 (1H, dt, $J_o=J_o$ 7.4, J_m 1.2, H-5), 2.59 (3H, s, 10-CH₃); ¹³C nmr δ 140.3 (C-3), 138.9 (C-12b), 136.67 (C-7a), 134.67 (C-3a), 134.03 (C-10, C-12a), 130 (C-7b), 127.58 (C-11a), 127.37 (C-7c), 129.91 (C-2), 128.64 (C-11), 127.37 (C-6), 126.91 (C-1), 126.20 (C-12), 126.14 (C-9), 123.74 (C-8), 123.47 (C-4), 121.41 (C-3), 119.57 (C-7), 21.68 (C₁₀-CH₃).

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